

REGULATORY CHALLENGES OF USING UNMANNED VESSELS

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Abstract

Since Munin project in 2012 to Yara Birkeland to start its commercial operations in 2022, the unmanned and completely autonomous ships have been discussion among maritime lawyers. There are several research papers written on the field; several discussions handled in various institutions. Yet, there is no ship today that is allowed to sail as a robot without a human onboard. This presentation aims to answer a following question – what are the aspects that withhold the policymakers to let the already tested ships to be used commercially as completely unmanned?

To answer the question, we based our research on social acceptance theory. We made a brief review of existing regulations in force in Nordic and Baltic countries. Second, we conducted literature review of current state of the technological readiness to use ships that are completely unmanned. The third step involves an empirical study through the questionnaires to understand social acceptance of such vehicles by public, maritime specialists as well as policymakers.

The preliminary results of our empirical study indicate that the regulators would prefer well defined laws and regulations for completely unmanned vessels, either complete automated or guided from remote control center. At the same time, the legislators are not ready to issue such regulations for various reasons - mainly due to lack of understanding how such vessels are controlled and how safety to the vessels, their cargo and surroundings is achieved.

Implications for sustainable maritime operation

Automation and digitalization of ships fulfills several sustainable development goals. Its biggest effect would be in decent working conditions and economic growth, the United Nations sustainable development goal (SDG) 8 - it would normalize the life of the mariners who do not need to work long days on board without going home to their families providing better working conditions as well as reducing possible errors due to fatigue and therefor reducing the need for repair costs. It also influences SDG14, life below water as lack of errors reduces possible danger for pollution and accident. In addition, technical systems provide better optimization for efficiency and reduced energy consumption due to no need for cooking, lighting, heating, air conditioning etc., fulfilling the SDG 13, climate action.